

Sonocatalytic degradation of a textile organic dye over the novel zeolite Y/NiTiO₃ nanocomposite catalyst from water media

Meysam Sadeghi

Faculty of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Iran

Email: MeysamSadeghi1364@gmail.com

Maryam Gholami

Faculty of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Iran

Email: Maryam.Gholami78@yahoo.com

Pourya Zarshenas

Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University (SBU), Iran

Email: PouryaZarshenas@yahoo.com

Abstract

The present research was carried out to ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal fabricate zeolite Y/NiTiO₃ nanocomposite for sonocatalysis of methylene blue (MB) from water media. The achieved outcomes of FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD, and VSM analyses affirmed proper fabricate of zeolite Y/NiTiO₃ nanocomposite displayed the highest sonocatalytic degradation efficiency of 98.9% at irradiation time of 30 min in the presence of the ultrasonic (US)/H₂O₂ system. The impacts of sonocatalyst amount and initial MB concentration on the degradation efficiency were investigated. Additionally, [•]OH radicals as the main reactive species during the sonodegradation reaction were distinguished. The degradation efficiency decreased only 6% after 4 repeated cycles. Therefore, zeolite Y/NiTiO₃ nanocomposite can be utilized as a promising sonocatalyst for the removal of organic dye contaminants with great reproducibility potential.

Keywords: Y/NiTiO₃, nanocomposite, catalyst, methylene blue (MB), sonodegradation.